

Lomi Lomi Massage in the Treatment of Endometriosis

RESEARCH REPORT

This report would not have been possible without Agnieszka Kawula – therapist and Lomi lomi massage teacher.

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Introduction

INTRODUCTION

When pain overshadows everything

Imagine a life in which every day brings pain—persistent, chronic, all-encompassing pain that restricts movement and drains energy. A life in which a woman is unable to function during her period and she must continuously take painkillers to get through the next few hours.

It is a time marked by frustration, often accompanied by years of fruitless diagnosis, during which the symptoms were downplayed. „That’s simply the way you are.“—they would say. „After she gives birth, it’ll end“. Those were times when hormone therapies either did not work or caused additional health problems. Chronic fatigue, persistent swelling, intestinal discomfort, mood swings. And the feeling that a woman's body was no longer her ally, that she was left to struggle alone, with a problem that no one wanted to understand.

For women with endometriosis, this is standard.

As a massage therapist with many years of experience, I often encountered the opinion that Lomi lomi is just a “relaxing massage.” However, my experience in the treatment room told me otherwise. I have repeatedly witnessed the profound therapeutic power of this technique.

Some of my clients, when talking about their health problems, mentioned that they suffer from endometriosis. They described how this disease destroys their quality of life on many levels.

Inspired by their confessions, I decided to check whether Lomi lomi massage could be a valuable tool for working with women suffering from endometriosis and whether it could have a tangible impact on improving their health and well-being.

This report was created out of the belief that women facing this disease deserve holistic support, understanding, and hope for a better life. It presents the results of a study in which a few dozen women with symptoms of endometriosis received a series of traditional Hawaiian Lomi lomi massages. Several other therapists joined the project. The participants of this study shared their feelings about the impact of Lomi lomi therapy on their pain levels, physical and emotional functioning, and quality of life in questionnaires which I designed specially for this purpose.

The results I share in this paper show that my experiences were not isolated. Lomi lomi therapists, regardless of whether they adhered to a more traditional approach to this technique or already had experience in using this massage as a therapeutic tool, unanimously agreed that the method worked very well as a therapy supporting the treatment of endometriosis.

Their findings are fully confirmed by the study participants. Analysis of the questionnaires they completed has led to the conclusion that they experienced.

Results

Dramatic reduction in pain and pharmacotherapy

Reduction of chronic pain: A statistically significant reduction in the intensity, duration, and frequency of pain symptoms, including pain associated with endometriosis, was observed.

Less dependence on medication: With each subsequent massage, both the number of people reaching for painkillers and the dose taken decreased. After the fourth session, only one in five women needed medication. Even when it was necessary to take them after the fifth massage, these were often single weaker tablets or symbolic doses, which meant a significant reduction in pharmacotherapy.

Reduction of other somatic symptoms: Participants also reported significant relief from muscle pain, somatic tension, migraines, and lymphatic oedema (most commonly in the abdomen, thighs, and calves), which resulted in a feeling of lightness and a slimmer body. Increased vitality and improved quality of life.

Enhanced energy levels and sleep quality: Energy levels systematically increased, ultimately resulting in a noticeable improvement. A significant improvement in sleep quality (easier falling asleep, deeper sleep, and less frequent awakenings) was consistently observed, which contributed to better regeneration.

Stress reduction: Lomi lomi massage proved to be an effective tool for reducing stress levels. Participants regained a sense of peace, composure, and increased patience in their personal and professional lives.

Holistic improvement in the quality of life: The quality and comfort of life improved significantly. The therapy inspired healthy lifestyle changes (e.g., discontinuation of stronger medications, reduction in consumption of sweets, increased physical activity). Emotional transformation and trust in the body.

Emotional well-being: Lomi lomi therapy initiated the process of releasing suppressed emotions, which could temporarily manifest itself in mood swings, but ultimately led to long-term emotional stability, greater awareness, and better stress management.

Body acceptance: The therapy had a predominantly positive effect on the participants' perception of their own bodies. They regained acceptance, love, and gratitude for their bodies, which were no longer perceived as a source of pain and limitations.

Safety and trust: The key therapeutic element was building a sense of safety and care in the relationship with the therapist, which allowed for deep relaxation and complete surrender to the process.

INTRODUCTION

Conclusions

The results of the study indicate that Lomi lomi massage is a highly effective, safe, and holistic form of non-pharmacological support in the treatment of endometriosis.

The therapeutic effect builds up progressively, reaching its peak at the end of the therapeutic cycle. It is not only a reduction in pain, but also a holistic change affecting the body, mind, and emotions—from physical relief, through improved sleep and energy, to emotional relief and a renewed relationship with one's own body.

For many participants, massage proved to be a turning point—the beginning of a journey to restore a sense of comfort in life, which they had not felt for years. Their accounts tell stories of regained joy, better sleep, and a noticeable increase in energy even after just a few sessions. Reading the surveys that came in over time, I was delighted to learn how women not only gained relief from pain, but also a sense of emotional stability and greater self-acceptance. The participants described it as not just a simple procedure, but a deep regeneration on many levels—somatic, mental, and in their relationship with themselves. Women with endometriosis have lived too long in the shadow of disbelief, stereotypes, and misunderstanding.

My plea to the medical community and the public is clear: we must stop downplaying our pain and treating suffering as the norm for women.

It is necessary to provide prompt, holistic diagnosis and create a support system—both medical and psychological – so that every patient feels cared for and listened to.

There is a pressing need for widespread education about how deeply endometriosis affects health, relationships, emotions, and daily functioning. Only by raising awareness among doctors and gaining their recognition of the symptoms, knowledge, and empathy can we break the vicious cycle, paving the way for women to live full lives, free from shame and loneliness. I believe that this voice will bring about measurable change where for years there has been only silence and misunderstanding.

The survey proved that Lomi lomi massage therapy can and should be treated as a valuable complementary therapy to conventional medical care, as it is a holistic tool for managing chronic pain, emotional stability, and restoring women's control over their health.

The full report contains detailed statistical analyses, a description of the massage therapy process, case studies, therapists' observations, and a discussion on the mechanisms of massage in the context of endometriosis.

I encourage you to read this story of pain, frustration, hope, transformation, and women's rediscovery of themselves.

Agnieszka Kawula

Endometriosis And Lomi Lomi Massage

ENDOMETRIOSIS AND LOMI LOMI MASSAGE

What is endometriosis

Endometriosis is a chronic gynaecological disease affecting approximately 10% of women of childbearing age worldwide, which is estimated to be around 176 million patients. In Poland, the problem affects 1-1.5 million women. However, despite its prevalence, the disease is still largely misunderstood and misdiagnosed.

Endometriosis is characterised by the presence of endometrium-like tissue outside the uterine cavity. It manifests itself primarily as pain—during menstruation, intercourse, and as chronic pelvic pain. The disease is also a major cause of infertility, affecting 30-50% of patients who have difficulty conceiving.

Problems with diagnosis

The most distressing aspect of this disease is the dramatic delay in diagnosis—on average, it takes 7-10 years from the first symptoms to diagnosis. Patients visit an average of five doctors before receiving the correct diagnosis.

These delays lead to progression of abnormalities, complications, and higher healthcare costs. Untreated endometriosis can lead to scar tissue, ovarian cysts, and damage to internal organs.

Delays are caused by many factors: downplaying symptoms as “a part of the female experience,” overlapping symptoms with other conditions, and the invasiveness of the diagnostic gold standard procedure—laparoscopy.

Chronic pain

Chronic pain is a central feature of endometriosis, affecting all aspects of life—from mental health to professional functioning. It leads to depression, anxiety, sleep disturbances, and feelings of social isolation. Women describe their pain as “devastating” and “paralysing.”

Socio-economic costs

Endometriosis generates enormous economic costs. In the US, the average annual cost of treatment is approximately \$16,573*—three times more than for women without the disease.

The EndoCost study estimated the average annual cost at €9,579 per patient. In Poland, patients bear the costs of private diagnostics, which can sometimes reach tens of thousands of PLN.

Indirect costs are significantly higher—67% of total costs are due to loss of productivity. Women with endometriosis lose an average of 6.3 hours of work per week, which equates to 6.6 days of absence and 31.8 days of reduced productivity per year.

In Europe, the annual socio-economic costs amount to €30 billion, and in the US, \$22 billion.

Manual therapies in the treatment of chronic pain

In the context of chronic pain and the insufficient effectiveness of conventional methods, supportive therapies, including manual therapies in particular, are attracting increasing attention.

They are highly effective in reducing chronic pain, decreasing muscle tension, and improving circulation. Manual therapy, such as massage, stimulates the parasympathetic nervous system, leading to lower cortisol levels, reduced tension, and improved sleep. Studies confirm that regular massage strengthens the immune system—it increases the number of immune cells (lymphocytes) and reduces the severity of inflammatory processes in the body.

The placebo mechanism is also interesting, which in manual therapies is an active neurophysiological process contributing to pain reduction. As for women's health, massage supports the functioning of the lymphatic system and may influence the regulation of the menstrual cycle by modulating the endocrine system.

Mechanisms of massage therapy

Massage works on many biological levels. It activates mechanoreceptors that modulate pain perception and stimulates the parasympathetic nervous system, reducing physiological stress. It affects the lymphatic system, reducing swelling and supporting detoxification. It modulates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, increasing the secretion of oxytocin and endorphins.

*Reference: Soliman AM, Surrey E, Bonafede M, Nelson JK, Castelli-Haley J. Real-World Evaluation of Direct and Indirect Economic Burden Among Endometriosis Patients in the United States. *Advances in Therapy*. 2018 Feb 15;35(3):408-423. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5859693>

ENDOMETRIOSIS
AND LOMI LOMI MASSAGE

Working with the fascia—a three-dimensional network of connective tissue that permeates the body—is also crucial. Manipulation of the fascia can restore proper sliding of the fascial layers, which is important in the context of endometriosis due to the formation of adhesions and tensions in the pelvis.

Lomi lomi massage: tradition and therapeutic principles

Lomi lomi is a traditional Hawaiian form of massage combining manual techniques with elements of spirituality. The name means “to change” or “to transform.” The practice was originally performed by kahunas—Hawaiian healers—as part of a holistic medical system.

The philosophy of Lomi lomi is based on the belief that the body, mind, and spirit are inseparably connected. The concept of “aloha”—love, compassion, and respect—is central to this philosophy.

The technique is characterised by long, flowing movements performed with the forearms and hands, which mimic ocean waves. The therapist can massage two parts of the body at the same time, which enhances deep relaxation.

Although most research on Lomi lomi is qualitative or ethnographic in nature, there is evidence of its effectiveness in improving circulation, reducing muscle tension, promoting lymphatic drainage, and supporting mental health.

The long, rhythmic movements characteristic of Lomi lomi can be particularly effective in stimulating the parasympathetic nervous system, leading to deep relaxation and stress reduction.

In the treatment of endometriosis, Lomi lomi massage can offer several key benefits: pain reduction through modulation of the nervous system, improved lymph and blood circulation, relaxation of tension in the pelvic and abdominal fascia, as well as emotional and psychological support through the creation of a safe, empathetic therapeutic space.

Reasons for and purpose of research on Lomi lomi massage in endometriosis

Due to the chronic nature of endometriosis, significant diagnostic delays, the limited effectiveness of many conventional therapies, and the enormous social and economic burden associated with this disease, there is an urgent necessity to seek new, complementary therapeutic approaches.

Limitations of current treatment

Standard treatment for endometriosis includes hormone therapy, painkillers (NSAIDs, opioids), and surgical interventions (laparoscopic removal of lesions). However, these methods have significant limitations: hormone therapy often causes unwanted side effects and is not effective in all patients, painkillers carry the risk of addiction and complications, and surgery, although

sometimes necessary, is invasive, expensive, and does not guarantee a permanent cure—recurrences are common.

Many patients with endometriosis report frustration over the lack of a holistic approach in conventional medicine—doctors often focus solely on treating physical symptoms, overlooking the psychological, emotional, and social aspects of the disease. Patients express a need for therapies that treat them as a whole, rather than just a collection of symptoms to be “fixed.”

With its holistic approach, Lomi lomi massage can be a valuable complement to conventional treatment. Initial observations suggest a significant reduction in pain and improvement in quality of life in women with endometriosis.

Purpose and rationale of the study

The aim of the study is to systematically evaluate the impact of Lomi lomi on pain intensity, sleep quality, energy levels, emotional functioning, and overall quality of life. If its effectiveness is confirmed, this could lead to the inclusion of this therapy in standard care protocols as a safe, non-invasive supportive method. The study responds to patients' pleas for holistic, empathetic care that goes beyond pharmacology and surgery, offering a potentially cost-effective method of improving quality of life and reducing absence from work.

Methodology, ethics and limitations of the study

METHODOLOGY, ETHICS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

How participants and therapists were selected

Study participants

The study included **82 women** aged 16–56 (mean age: 37.4 years; median: 38 years) who had been diagnosed with or were suspected of having endometriosis. The largest group consisted of women aged 36–45 (35 people).

Recruitment took place mainly through social media, referrals, and support groups for women with endometriosis.

The selection of participants for the study was self-recruitment-based—any woman interested in participating could express her wish to do so, which resulted in voluntary participation.

The inclusion criteria were:

- diagnosis or suspicion of endometriosis,
- reported pain,
- over 16 years of age,
- consent to refrain from starting other manual therapies during the study.

The participants represented a variety of professions—from healthcare workers (doctors, physical therapists, nurses) to teachers and educators, artists, business professionals, IT specialists, administrators, and service providers.

Some of the participants were on disability pension or were not working due to health reasons.

Therapists

The study involved **35 Lomi lomi massage therapists** with varying degrees of experience—from 2 months to 16 years of practice (average: 4.25 years; median: 2.75 years).

They can be divided into three groups:

- beginners (less than 1 year—7 people),
- intermediate (1–5 years—17 people),
- advanced (more than 5 years—6 people).

The average session duration was approximately 91 minutes (ranging from 60 to 120 minutes). Each therapist treated an average of 2.1 patients (median: 2 patients). All five massage sessions were performed over a period of **2–2,5 months**.

Test protocol and measurement tools

Each participant underwent a series of five Lomi lomi massage sessions. Measurements were taken using self-assessment questionnaires completed by the participants before the start of therapy, 24 hours immediately after each massage, and 5–6 days after the session.

The questionnaires included questions about pain levels, well-being, energy, sleep quality, and the need for pain medication, rated on a scale of 0–10.

Additionally, therapists submitted their own questionnaires after completing the series, describing the changes observed in patients.

METHODOLOGY, ETHICS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Consent and voluntary participation

- Before starting the study, each participant received clear, accessible information about the course of therapy, potential benefits, and possible effects, which built a sense of confidence and empowerment.
- During the appointments, it was repeatedly emphasised that participation is entirely voluntary, and that withdrawing without giving a reason will not negatively affect the relationship with the therapeutic team or further care.
- The fact that the therapy was free of charge eliminated financial concerns, allowing every woman to focus on her own health and well-being, regardless of her financial situation.
- The study also emphasised the importance of receiving reliable feedback from participants so that they could make informed decisions about the course and evolution of therapy. This approach strengthened the partnership and encouraged participants to share both positive and difficult experiences.

Anonymity and confidentiality

- Each participant was assured that her personal data and sensitive medical information would be stored in a manner that guaranteed complete anonymity. Only encrypted and isolated archives were used for data processing, and access to them was restricted to only those directly involved in the analysis.

- Both during the collection of questionnaires and the analysis of results, emphasis was placed on maintaining confidentiality and protecting privacy—even detailed descriptions of experiences did not allow for the identification of any of the women.
- Regular reminders about their right to decide which information and insights could be anonymously included in the study results helped participants build awareness of their boundaries and relieve any burden associated with disclosing personal experiences.
- Confidentiality also encouraged openness in sharing emotions and thoughts—many women emphasised that the knowledge of anonymity gave them the courage to speak honestly about difficult experiences that had previously been kept silent.

Therapeutic relationship

- The key element was building trust, respect for boundaries, and empathy in the therapist-patient relationship.
- The therapists emphasised the importance of creating a safe space where participants could freely share their feelings and information about their ailments.
- Professionalism, warmth, empathy, and open communication before and after sessions were the foundation of the therapeutic relationship.

Research ethics

METHODOLOGY, ETHICS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Research limitations

Lack of control group and randomization

The study did not have a control group. Randomisation was also not used. All participants received the same intervention (Lomi lomi massage), which makes it impossible to compare the effects with a group that did not undergo therapy or received a placebo.

The subjective nature of measurements

The assessments were based on the participants' self-evaluation on a scale of 0-10, which introduces an element of subjectivity. There are no objective medical measures here—no imaging tests were performed, and no inflammatory markers or other clinical parameters were measured.

Self-recruitment and selection bias

Participants volunteered to take part in the study, which could have led to selection bias—the study attracted people interested in complementary therapies and open to a holistic approach to health, which may limit the representativeness of the sample.

Incomplete data

Several participants discontinued the study before completing five sessions. Reasons included logistical issues (difficulties with scheduling, transportation), health issues (inflammation, starting hormone treatment, hospitalisation), psychological issues (anxiety, pressure from partner, mental health issues), and lack of commitment or motivation.

Influence of external factors

The influence of external factors such as stress, diet, other concurrent therapies, or medications used was not controlled. Participants took a variety of medications (hormonal, painkillers, thyroid medication, insulin resistance medication) and supplements (vitamin D3, magnesium, omega-3), which may have affected the results.

The inability to separate the placebo effect and the therapeutic relationship

It was impossible to separate the effect of the massage itself from the placebo effect and the influence of the therapeutic relationship. Building trust, empathy, and a sense of care may have contributed to the improvement in well-being.

Limited generalisability of results

The specificity of the study group (self-recruitment, interest in complementary therapies) limits the possibility of generalising the results to the entire population of women with endometriosis. The diversity of therapists' experience (ranging from 2 months to 16 years) may also have influenced the quality of the intervention and the results obtained.

Lack of long-term observation

The study only included a series of five sessions—no long-term follow-up was conducted to assess how long the effects of therapy lasted after its completion.

Course and results of the study

Participants' perspective

Typical participant in the study

- **Age** - 37-38 years old
- **Reason for coming in for the study** - seeking pain relief, improving quality of life, negative experiences with medication
- **Concerns about the form of therapy** - physical discomfort, emotional reaction to touch, organisational issues
- **Onset of symptoms** - sedentary lifestyle, stress, injuries, infections, along with the onset of menstruation
- **Diagnosis and treatment** - long and frustrating diagnostic process, lack of empathy from medical staff; negative experiences with hormone therapies; loss of trust in conventional medicine
- **Characteristics of menstruation** - heavy, painful, and profuse; often preventing normal functioning; the need to take strong painkillers; irregular cycles
- **Mood and energy levels** - low to moderate; chronic fatigue
- **Pain** - multidimensional, varying in intensity and location; limits functioning and affects emotional state
- **Impact of illness on life** - problems with daily functioning, frequent sick leave, social isolation, problems at work and in relationships

- **Sleep** - average sleep quality, frequent problems falling asleep
- **Eating habits and diet** - varied appetite, periods of craving sweets, general preference for healthy eating, following elimination diets
- **Oedema** - swelling and lymphatic oedema, most commonly in the abdominal area
- **Bowel movements** - diarrhoea, constipation
- **Attention span and stress** - medium attention span, high levels of everyday stress
- **Rest and relaxation** - tries to rest on weekends, in some cases every day; the most common forms of relaxation are mental activities, contact with nature, passive rest, and body care
- **Massage experiences** - positive experiences with relaxation massages; mixed reception of physiotherapy; negatively perceived massages causing severe pain
- **Perception of one's own body** - the disease leads to a negative view of one's own body due to changes in appearance, pain levels, and physical limitations
- **Doctors' words remembered** - mostly negative and dismissive, rarely positive and empathetic
- **Reactions of those around you** - lack of understanding

The goal of therapy – reducing pain, improving quality of life, learning to cope with the disease

Key indicators before commencing the study

COURSE AND RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Additional data

Symptoms of the disease and their impact on the lives of the participants

Main physical complaints

- The most characteristic symptom of the disease was pain. The women described it as “long-lasting, severe, lasting from several to a dozen or so days a month.” Some women characterised the pain as permanent.
- The pain was concentrated around the abdomen and lower abdomen. In addition, there was pain in the back (especially in the lumbar region), pelvis, and hips. Some women also experienced frequent headaches or prolonged migraines.
- Menstruation was usually very painful. It was accompanied by heavy bleeding. These symptoms were so severe that a significant proportion of the respondents were unable to perform even the simplest everyday activities during this time.
- The illness was not limited to pain only. Participants also struggled with sleep problems, low energy levels, and accompanying chronic fatigue.

- Intestinal problems (bloating, constipation, diarrhea) and lymphatic oedema, most often in the abdomen, were also common.
- To relieve the pain, women used painkillers on an ad hoc basis. Many of them did so very often, some every day.
- In addition, women often used complex pharmacological and supplementation therapies, including hormonal drugs and medications for comorbidities such as thyroid disorders or insulin resistance.
- Some of the respondents sought relief in home remedies, the most popular of which are rest and heat (hot water bottles, warm baths).

Impact of the disease on personal and professional life

- The vast majority of women surveyed (over 80%) experienced a negative impact of the disease on their lives.
- The pain was often so severe that it made normal life practically impossible.

- The disease made it difficult to perform professional duties and led to a noticeable decrease in efficiency. A significant group of women had to take sick leave or leave on request due to periodic exacerbation of symptoms.
- A common side effect of the disease was social isolation. Women avoided social and family gatherings. The disease also led to problems in relationships with loved ones and a feeling that those around them did not understand their situation.
- Endometriosis had a negative impact on emotional well-being, causing psychological distress, mood swings, stress, anxiety, and depression.
- Participants also reported negative perceptions of their own bodies due to pain, swelling, and bloating (known as the “endo belly”).
- Many women felt that they lost control over their own bodies.

Diagnostic barriers and lack of empathy on the part of doctors

A. The diagnostic journey and frustration associated with treatment

- Most respondents indicated years of delays in obtaining a correct diagnosis.
- Patients felt helpless in the face of the ineffectiveness of conventional therapies, including hormone treatment, which not only failed to produce the expected results but also caused unacceptable side effects, such as persistent, long-lasting swelling and changes in body appearance.
- Due to the low effectiveness of conventional medicine, patients often sought help on their own, turning to natural medicine, osteopathy, traditional Chinese medicine, yoga, or complementary therapies such as Lomi lomi massage.

B. Perception of endometriosis symptoms by physicians

- The participants described their doctors' appointments as frustrating and fruitless. Gynaecologists' comments on the symptoms described by the participants were mostly negative and dismissive. Some of the women wrote explicitly about their words being belittled or ignored. The most common comment was: "That's just the way you are" or "That's just a part of you."
- Many patients encountered situations where their symptoms were attributed to stress. They were often advised to see a psychologist or psychiatrist.
- It was very common for doctors to suggest pregnancy as a cure: "Once she gives birth, it will go away." Such comments were received negatively, especially by women for whom getting pregnant was a problem.

- The participants also remembered pessimistic diagnoses such as: "There is no cure for this" or "It will only get worse." Many respondents felt neglected, misunderstood, and left to fend for themselves during the treatment process.

Changes after the first massage

For most women, their first Lomi lomi session was a new, deeply positive experience that brought immediate relief and a sense of care, and initiated intense processes throughout the body. The massage itself was often perceived as “a completely different dimension of massage.”

- **Changes in general mood and self-acceptance:** According to the participants, the massage led to deep relaxation and stress relief. Their general mood after the massage was stable. Some experienced temporary fatigue.
- **Changes in pain intensity:** The level of “usual” pain within 24 hours after massage remained moderate. In some women, it disappeared, while in others it decreased significantly (hips, back, lower abdomen). Several women reported milder menstruation, and several experienced intermittent relief from their chronic pain.
- **Changes in the body's physiology:** The first session was characterised by strong self-cleansing processes in the body. Patients urinated much more frequently than before, experienced increased sweating (especially at night), and felt thirsty. Some people experienced mild, temporary symptoms resembling a cold, a feeling of muscle soreness, or weakness, which was interpreted as a reaction to the body's work. These reactions, although perceived as strong and violent, usually subsided after a few days.
- **Changes in energy levels, focus, and sleep quality:** In the evening on the day of the massage, energy levels varied from very high to very low. Throughout the following days, most women rated their energy levels as stable, although some of them experienced a feeling of “lack of power” and a need for regeneration. Sleep quality in the first week after the massage was rated as better. Some of the respondents noted that they slept deeper and longer.
- **Emotional changes:** Nearly half of the respondents experienced temporary mood swings, irritability, or emotional instability, which was interpreted as the beginning of the process of releasing suppressed emotions. At the same time, some women experienced a sense of “greater ease,” inner joy, peace, and emotional cleansing.

Changes after the second massage

The second massage session deepened the feeling of relaxation and trust in the therapist. The participants began to “let go” of control over the course of therapy. The physiological reactions of the body were even stronger than during the first session. In some cases, strong emotions related to the illness, which had been suppressed until then, were released.

- **Changes in general mood and self-acceptance:** Compared to the first session, overall mood improved significantly a few days after the second massage. The participants continued to emphasise that they felt noticed and cared for. The first reflections on positive changes in appearance (e.g., “my belly has gotten flatter”) began to appear. The women reported that they were more aware of their bodies and better able to cope with stress.
- **Changes in pain intensity:** The participants unanimously agreed that their level of “usual” pain decreased further. The percentage of people who had to take painkillers in the following days was lower than after the first massage. Women more often reported a complete elimination of pain in the lower abdomen. Pain that occurred occasionally was mainly concentrated in other areas (e.g., back pain).
- **Changes in the body's physiology:** The signs of detoxification (more frequent urination, thirst, sweating) became more intensified. Some participants experienced severe fatigue that lasted more than one day. The women also observed changes in their menstrual cycles (e.g., earlier periods, less pain, and the expulsion of clots). They interpreted this as further deep cleansing of the body.

- **Changes in energy levels, focus, and sleep quality:** The overall energy level of the participants was higher than after the first massage session and remained high over the following days. Sleep quality also improved, indicating that massage contributes to increased relaxation.
- **Emotional changes:** The second session was highly therapeutic; there were cases of deep emotional release, including anger, sadness, and frustration. A large group of participants experienced strong mood swings. On the other hand, many women wrote in the questionnaires that they felt greater peace and inner joy, and that their thinking was becoming much more positive.

Changes after the third massage

The third massage often marked a critical point, characterised by a temporary decline in well-being among some participants, which may have been related to intensified detoxification and adaptation processes in the body. At the same time, this session brought about the deepest relaxation, increased emotional stability, and a continuation of positive therapeutic changes.

- **Changes in general mood and self-acceptance:** In the week following the massage, there was a noticeable, although temporary, deterioration in the general mood of more than half of the participants, who considered this to be a reaction to the intense adaptation and detoxification processes. Despite this, their acceptance of their own bodies increased. The participants began to perceive themselves as “slimmer” and “lighter,” and the massages motivated them to take better care of themselves.
- **Changes in pain intensity:** The level of “usual” pain continued to decline. There was a reduction in menstrual pain (measured by a lower need for painkillers, shorter duration, and lighter blood colour). More than half of the participants felt no pain at all or only very mild pain. The pain that did occur was perceived more as “muscle soreness” or subtle prickling and was seen as the body’s response to physical activity.
- **Changes in the body's physiology:** Detoxification symptoms, such as sweating, increased bowel movements, and a specific, not always pleasant body odour, were most severe after the first massage and clearly decreased after the third, giving way to more frequent urination and increased thirst.

- **Changes in energy levels, focus, and sleep quality:** The vast majority of respondents reported a further increase in energy levels, which persisted for a long time. Participants also observed a significant improvement in sleep quality: most women said they fell asleep faster, their sleep was deeper, and nighttime awakenings were much less frequent. They remembered their dreams more often.
- **Emotional changes:** After the third massage session, the participants observed progressive emotional stabilisation; the vast majority felt a deeper sense of calm, tranquility, and reduced levels of irritation and anger. A few still experienced temporary emotional instability or irritability, which was part of the active process of releasing emotions.

Changes after the fourth massage

The fourth session was often the culmination of the therapeutic effect, bringing participants the most relief from pain and reinforcing changes at the physiological and emotional levels.

- **Changes in general mood and self-acceptance:** Overall well-being improved dramatically in the week after the fourth massage, returning to high levels after a temporary decline after the third session. Body acceptance increased, with visible changes such as a reduction in so called "pregnancy belly" and swelling. There was a greater sense of confidence and harmony.
- **Changes in pain intensity:** The level of "usual" pain during the day and week after the fourth massage reached the lowest average values in the entire therapy cycle, which indicated the maximum therapeutic effect. More than half of the subjects felt no pain or described it as significantly lighter. The need for painkillers decreased; only one in four people needed any pharmacological support.
- **Changes in the body's physiology:** The symptoms of detoxification subsided and became milder. There was still a tendency toward increased thirst and more frequent urination. Visible physical changes were noted, such as a reduction in lumps (fibromas) and general relaxation in the body.
- **Changes in energy levels, focus, and sleep quality:** The overall energy level increased once again. The participants in the study were much more eager to try new activities and felt a surge of strength that allowed them to cope with everyday life without any problems.
- **Emotional changes:** The fourth massage brought deep relaxation and emotional peace. The women described it as a state of "greater clarity and brightness." The massage helped release sadness and build self-confidence. The ability to set healthy boundaries in relationships increased. The women surveyed more often felt a long-lasting sense of calm and greater distancing from stressful situations.

Changes after the fifth massage

The fifth massage was seen as the conclusion of the therapeutic process, often leading to the deepest relaxation, complete surrender, and the highest level of well-being.

- **Changes in general mood and self-acceptance:** Overall comfort and quality of life improved significantly, achieving the highest average rating in the entire study. Well-being after the fifth massage was the best of all sessions. After completing the therapy, acceptance of one's own body increased. Participants perceived their bodies as lighter, slimmer, and free of tension.
- **Changes in pain intensity:** The participants reported that the therapy significantly reduced the number of "very painful days." They experienced severe pain not only less frequently, but also less intensely. Four people reported complete pain relief. The use of painkillers was incidental, and the doses were significantly lower. **Pain no longer interfered with daily functioning.**
- **Changes in the body's physiology:** The therapy had a very positive effect on reducing lymphatic oedema in the abdomen, thighs, and calves. Some of the study participants systematically measured their circumferences and were pleased to note that their bodies were becoming slimmer. The massage also had a positive effect on optimizing digestive processes and bowel movement frequency. Their bodies began to "function properly" again. The participants more often felt light and satisfied with their bodies.
- **Changes in energy levels, focus, and sleep quality:** Energy levels and sleep quality remained at their highest levels, indicating sustained regeneration of the body. The average energy level rating was significantly higher than before therapy. Concentration and focus levels also improved.
- **Emotional changes:** The participants in the study observed a significant reduction in their stress levels, which resulted in them entering a state of relaxation and tranquillity more quickly, which in turn contributed to an improvement in their ability to cope with life's challenges. The women gained greater peace of mind and composure. Their self-esteem, body acceptance, and ability to set boundaries also improved.

COURSE AND RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Comprehensive summary of the survey results

Reducing pain and physical healing: A statistically significant reduction in the intensity, duration, and frequency of pain symptoms was observed, including pain associated with endometriosis and painful menstruation. Participants also reported significant relief from muscle pain, somatic tension, migraines, and other specific ailments, indicating the broad spectrum of analgesic effects of Lomi lomi massage.

Physiological function optimisation: The therapy contributed to a reduction in lymphatic oedema and water retention in the body, as confirmed by both subjective feelings (lightness of the body, reduction in swelling) and objective changes in body circumference (especially in the abdomen, thighs, and calves). An improvement in breathing comfort was also observed in a significant proportion of the subjects, as well as a normalisation of bowel movements. Increased thirst and intense sweating were interpreted as indicators of the activation of detoxification processes.

Increased vitality and improved sleep quality: Energy levels improved significantly, with a predominant increase in vitality among most participants. A consistent improvement in sleep quality was observed (easier falling asleep, deeper sleep, and fewer nighttime awakenings), which directly resulted in better regeneration of the body.

Emotional stabilisation and self-awareness development: Lomi lomi massage showed to have a powerful stress-reducing effect, leading to deeper relaxation, calmness, and an increased ability to cope with everyday challenges. The therapy also initiated processes of releasing suppressed emotions, which, despite temporary discomfort, resulted in long-term emotional stability, increased focus, and a deeper connection with one's own body and intuition.

The uniqueness of the Lomi lomi massage technique: The study highlights the uniqueness of the Lomi lomi technique, which is characterised by a holistic approach to the entire body, smooth and continuous movements performed with the forearms, and the absence of pain during the session. A key element of the therapy was building deep trust and a sense of security in the relationship with the therapist, which enabled full immersion in the process and maximised the therapeutic benefits.

Impact on quality of life and health-promoting changes: The therapy proved to be a catalyst for positive changes in the participants' lifestyles, inspiring them to become more mindful of their bodies, improve their eating and sleeping habits, increase their physical activity, and work more actively with their emotions. These changes had a holistic impact on quality of life, encompassing personal, professional, and interpersonal relationships. The participants' declared willingness to continue Lomi lomi therapy as an integral part of their health care is evidence of its lasting value and positive impact.

The importance of monitoring and perception of time: Regular completion of questionnaires after massages was an important therapeutic element that promoted deeper self-observation, self-reflection, and conscious monitoring of changes. Although the duration of therapy was often described as short, the study participants consistently rated it as supportive and effectively used, indicating an optimal pace of intervention.

Key indicators after completion of the study

Observations of participants who discontinued therapy

- **Quantitative analysis** of data from participants who completed the study after one or two sessions provides valuable insights into initial responses to therapy. Despite the shortened intervention period, a number of positive changes were noted, demonstrating the potential of Lomi lomi even in the short run.
- Quantitative data indicate a significant decrease in pain. "Usual pain" was reduced, and some women stopped feeling it altogether.
- An overall improvement in mood and sleep quality was also observed.
- **Qualitative analysis** revealed that the key experience, even with such brief contact, was a strong sense of "safety and care."
- After the second session, participants reported a "deeper experience," greater ease, and increasing relaxation of the body.
- Physiological reactions, such as frequent urination or increased sweating, occurred as often as in participants who underwent full therapy. Their intensity decreased after the second session, suggesting rapid adaptation of the body.
- These results indicate that even single sessions of Lomi lomi massage can initiate health-promoting processes, both by providing short-term pain relief and by building a foundation of therapeutic trust.

Therapists' perspective

Introduction

- The perspective of Lomi lomi therapists as direct witnesses to the therapeutic process provides a unique and extremely valuable complementary source of data to that collected from patients.
- Their observations, which often detect subtle changes in posture, skin color, or energy levels, confirm the subjective observations of patients described in the previous section.
- Their observations not only confirm the participants' feelings, but also shed light on changes that may have escaped the attention of the patients themselves.
- Thanks to the therapists' statements, we can follow the dynamics of changes occurring in patients from the perspective of those administering therapy, as well as learn about the challenges and emotions accompanying work with women struggling with the symptoms of endometriosis.

Basic statistical data

- **Number of therapists:** Thirty-five Lomi lomi massage therapists (both women and men) participated in the study.
- **Professional experience:** The therapists' work experience varied, with an average of approximately 4 years of practice (median ~2.5 years). The group included 7 beginners (less than one year of experience), 17 intermediate therapists (1-5 years), and 6 experienced therapists (more than 5 years of practice).
- **Time duration of a session:** A standard single Lomi lomi session lasted approximately 90 minutes on average. Ninety minutes was most often reported as the typical duration of the treatment (the median was exactly 90 minutes). Some massages were shorter (60 minutes), others longer (105-120 minutes), depending on the therapist's style and the patient's needs.
- **Number of patients per therapist:** Each massage therapist usually cared for 2 study participants (average of 2.1 patients per therapist; median 2). Most therapists worked with 1-3 women; the author of the study treated 10 patients, which was an exception.

Number of therapists

35

Professional experience
(average)

4 years

Average duration of
massage

90 minutes

Number of patients
per therapist (average)

2,1

Highest number of
patients per therapist

10

Motivations for participating in the study

- **The desire to help women with endometriosis:** Many massage therapists were motivated by a desire to bring relief to their suffering patients and provide real support for their health. "I know how many women struggle with the pain associated with endometriosis... I would like the results of the study to reach the right people and do a lot of good," wrote one of the therapists.
- **Trust in the therapeutic potential of Lomi lomi:** Therapists wanted to demonstrate that Lomi lomi is more than just a relaxing massage—that it can have a measurable healing effect on the body and emotions. One of them pointed out that endometriosis is a serious and often underestimated issue, so "the combination of Lomi and endo is spot on."
- **Personal experience:** Some of the massage therapists had a first-hand connection to the problem—they themselves suffered from endometriosis or had loved ones struggling with the disease. These therapists wanted to help others facing a similar challenge. "I suffered from endometriosis myself. So I wanted to support other women," emphasised one of the massage therapists. Another admitted, "I had a problem with endometriosis myself years ago. You just have to live with it." Sometimes the motivation was family—"My inspiration was my sister, who has been struggling with endometriosis for over a decade. Her health has improved significantly thanks to my massages."
- **Curiosity and desire to learn:** Some therapists joined out of pure scientific and professional curiosity—they wanted to see what effect regular sessions would have, and at the same time gain experience working with this demanding group of patients. "Out of curiosity to see the effect of Lomi massage on the body + to practice massage," admitted one of the massage therapists. Another wrote bluntly: "I was curious to see what would happen after a series of massages focused on endometriosis."
- **Elevating the status of Lomi lomi:** Several massage therapists wanted to obtain scientific confirmation of the effectiveness of Lomi lomi in order to raise the prestige of this method. They saw participation in the study as an opportunity to show that it is a serious therapy with real health benefits. "It is important for me to raise the profile of this massage, and I am firmly grounded in the scientific method," said one of the participants. Another therapist added: "I want Lomi to be seen as a serious tool for working with other people, one that has a real impact on human health and well-being."
- **Supporting the project (doing good):** For some therapists, the altruistic aspect was important: "I admire this wonderful initiative and wanted to make a modest contribution to doing good," admitted one of the massage therapists. Another mentioned her inner sense of mission: "A calling, intuition, a desire to support a cause that moved me and that I felt made a lot of sense."
- **Sense of community:** Several therapists emphasised that they wanted to be part of the therapeutic community and participate in something bigger that would allow them to share their experience. "I wanted to feel part of the therapeutic community," wrote one of the massage therapists.
- **Inclusiveness and empathy:** One of the therapists pointed out the need to also provide care for transgender and non-binary people who also suffer from female diseases. He wanted to create a safe space for them and broaden the perspective of the study. "The most important reason is to bring in the perspective that endometriosis affects not only women, but also non-binary and trans men. I care about inclusiveness and creating safe spaces where every person and every body can receive tender touch and empathy."

Observations of changes in patients

The massage therapists' accounts paint a vivid picture of the changes that occurred in the patients during subsequent Lomi lomi sessions. Therapists often noticed subtle effects that the participants themselves may not have recorded in the questionnaires. The most important changes observed included categories such as:

- **Physical improvement:** Most patients experienced a reduction in pain—massage therapists repeatedly noted a decrease in pelvic and abdominal pain, sometimes so significant that women stopped taking painkillers. This was accompanied by a general improvement in physical well-being: better sleep, more energy on a daily basis, reduction of swelling, and even improved digestion. The patients' bodies became more relaxed and softer with each treatment—therapists mentioned a reduction in muscle tension, softening of tissues, and in several cases, the disappearance of previously noticeable thickening or lumps in the body. There were also indications of massage's impact on the reproductive system—some women reported lighter bleeding during their periods and less menstrual pain, which made them feel better during their “difficult days.”
- **Changes in emotions and mental state:** The massage therapists observed an improvement in the participants' mood and overall emotional well-being. With each session, the patients became more cheerful, smiled more, and felt more joy, which was also noticed by their loved ones. Their acceptance of their own bodies and self-confidence also increased—thanks to the massages, several women grew to like their bodies more and regained a sense of control in dealing with their illness. The therapists described how the patients learned to listen to their bodies' signals and pay attention to their physical and emotional needs. For some women, the massage triggered the release of deeply hidden emotions. For the massage therapists, these reactions were proof that Lomi lomi works holistically, helping not only the patients' bodies but also their minds.
- **Changes in behaviour and attitude:** According to the therapists, the participants gradually opened up more and more—both to the massage process itself and in their communication. The massage therapists noticed growing openness and trust on the part of the women. With each subsequent visit, they were more willing to share their feelings and were more honest and trusting. They often expressed their delight at the effects of the massage and thanked the therapists for their help, which was very motivating for the therapists. What's more, they noticed that during therapy, patients got more involved in the healing process—massage therapists described cases where women took extra steps to improve their health between sessions (changing their diet, exercising, seeing a doctor). Several of them decided to take important life steps or make changes in their daily habits, which therapists interpreted as a sign that they were regaining control over their lives.
- **Pace and course of the process:** The massage therapists noted that the process of change was individual for each patient. Some responded sooner—after just 1-2 massages, they felt significant relief. Others needed more time and went through temporary crises (e.g., emotional breakdown or increased pain) before improvement occurred. This variability in the healing process was a valuable lesson in humility for the massage therapists—each body responded at its own pace and in its own way. Building trust and creating a safe space for the patient to experience these changes proved to be crucial. Ultimately, almost all therapists emphasised the holistic nature of the improvement: massage simultaneously impacted the body, well-being, and attitude of patients, providing them with both physical relief and emotional comfort.

Therapists' feedback after completing the study

After completing the series of massages, the therapists unanimously agreed that participating in the project had given them a great deal of satisfaction. The massage therapists derived deep satisfaction primarily from the visible progress made by their patients. The surveys repeatedly mentioned that the greatest reward for the therapists was the improvement in the women's health:

- reducing their pain and other symptoms of endometriosis,
- better sense of well-being,
- resuming daily activities.

Below you will find the most important sources of satisfaction mentioned by massage therapists:

- **Pain relief and improvement in patients' condition:** The most motivating factor for therapists was observing the reduction of pain in women. Seeing a patient suffer less from session to session brought great joy and a sense of purpose to their work. Moreover, massage therapists welcomed every sign of improvement—better sleep, increased energy, or reduction of other ailments.

- **Emotional transformation and bonding with the patient:** They found great satisfaction in being able to personally observe the positive transformation of their patients. The women participating in the study became more cheerful, relaxed, and regained their self-confidence. The therapists felt that they were contributing to this transformation. It was also important to build a close, trusting relationship: the massage therapists saw how the patients opened up to them more and more with each subsequent session. This bond based on trust and security was a source of professional fulfilment for them.
- **Gratitude and positive feedback:** The massage therapists emphasised that they were greatly encouraged by the gratitude shown by their patients—both direct thanks and information that the patients' loved ones had noticed an improvement in their condition. Hearing how delighted the women were with the effects of the massage and their desire to continue the therapy reinforced the therapists' belief in the value of their work. The fact that many participants asked about the possibility of further massages after the study ended was the best proof of the value of their efforts for the massage therapists.
- **Sense of purpose and mission:** Participation in the project gave massage therapists a sense of agency—the awareness that their work had actually improved the quality of life of particular individuals. Many of them had entered the profession and the study precisely for this reason—to help others—so seeing tangible results brought them deep professional satisfaction. Some pointed out that the results of the project strengthened their belief in the Lomi lomi method – they were able to see firsthand how much good this massage can do for people who are suffering. This, in turn, motivated them even more to further develop their skills and continue working with patients with similar problems.

Key challenges in the therapeutic process

1. Logistics and organisation

- Difficulties in coordinating schedules and limited availability of both parties
- Maintaining regular intervals between sessions
- Discipline in completing surveys; frequent reminders about the need to complete questionnaires

2. Attitude and commitment of patients

- Skepticism at the beginning (will this massage help?)
- Low motivation among some individuals; treating participation as a "free massage" (applies to individuals who have not completed therapy)
- Difficulty relaxing and handing over control during the procedure
- Concise, not very useful responses from patients in surveys

3. Emotions and therapeutic relationship

- The need to build trust and a sense of security at the beginning of the project
- Support during emotional crises and temporary intensification of symptoms
- Perceiving the departure of certain patients as a personal failure

- Working with deep emotions and trauma while maintaining one's own balance

4. Technical and physical challenges

- Adapting techniques to individual limitations (e.g., after medical interventions)
- Physical strain caused by long sessions; the need for ergonomic working conditions
- Practical issues: ensuring privacy, additional coverings, organising the workspace

5. Other issues

- Combining paid work with volunteering in the project; exhaustion
- The necessity of not transferring personal problems to the therapeutic relationship
- Communication and worldview differences that hinder understanding
- Uncertainty about the results and fear of not meeting expectations
- Occasional feeling of being taken advantage of in the absence of patient engagement (especially those who did not complete therapy)

Case studies

CASE STUDIES

Introduction

Endometriosis is a condition that extends far beyond menstrual pain alone. It is a disease that often limits personal and professional life, causing chronic fatigue and feelings of isolation. What's more, patients face a lack of understanding (both in their immediate environment and in doctors' offices).

Below are the experiences of several women who participated in a research program using Lomi lomi massage as a form of complementary therapy.

Although Lomi lomi seems to be exceptionally gentle and pleasant, it is a powerful intervention in the body that activates intense biochemical processes. For many participants, this technique proved to be not only a way to achieve deep relaxation, but above all a way to feel cared for and understood.

The study aimed to closely examine how the body and mind respond to this therapy over time. Analysis of the experience after each of the five sessions showed that Lomi lomi massage contributed to significant changes:

- **Decreased pain:** Many women reported fewer painful days and less intense symptoms, even those directly related to the disease.
- **Enhanced well-being and energy:** Participants often reported increased energy, relief from chronic fatigue, and inner calm. Some also experienced relief from symptoms not directly related to endometriosis, such as migraines, arrhythmia, and fibromyalgia symptoms.
- **Emotional and physiological release:** The massage triggered cleansing processes manifested by physiological reactions (e.g., sweating, increased thirst, changes in bowel movements), as well as emotional transformations—one of the women experienced a breakthrough, after which she became pregnant.

The following CASE STUDIES present in detail the individual paths of five participants, documenting their impressions and the changes that took place in their lives during this unique experiment with Hawaiian Lomi lomi massage.

CASE STUDIES

Klaudia

CASE STUDIES – KLAUDIA

Age 33 years	Duration of migraines 22 years	Duration of arrhythmia 5 years	Number of days with pain 11-20 per month
Menstruation: heavy, irregular, painful			
Therapy objective: "Reduce migraines, regulate heart rhythm, reduce pain and mental anxiety"			

Klaudia

- Klaudia—a 33-year-old manager with a long history of chronic pain that has accompanied her for most of her adult life. Five years before the study, she was diagnosed with cardiac arrhythmia, which placed an additional strain on her body.
- She began the study in a state of profound physical and mental exhaustion. Her daily life was dominated by pain and chronic stress.
- Most key indicators of quality of life were low. This was particularly the case for energy levels, sleep quality, and ability to concentrate.
- Klaudia lived in a state of constant tension, which worsened all her physical ailments and created a vicious circle: pain generated stress, and stress intensified pain.
- During her period, she took two to six painkillers a day, plus other meds for migraines and arrhythmia. This intense drug therapy showed how desperate she was to deal with her daily discomfort and how there weren't any better ways to manage her pain.
- Her health had a huge impact on all areas of her life. Endometriosis caused her to avoid intimacy, and migraines isolated her socially—she avoided meeting people. Sometimes she had to take time off work because of menstrual pain, which made her feel even more guilty and disabled.

CASE STUDIES – KLAUDIA

Klaudia's therapy was dynamic in nature, initially characterised by intense physiological–detoxification–and emotional reactions, which eventually gave way to profound and lasting improvement.

Massage 1: Release of tension and physiological reactions

- The first session was described as very pleasant and safe. Klaudia felt less tension in her shoulders and less pain in her shoulder blade. She also noticed that her stomach was less bloated than usual and her breathing had improved significantly.
- The massage also triggered strong biochemical processes manifested by:
 - intense sweating and thirst;
 - fluctuating body temperature (sometimes elevated, sometimes lowered);
 - the emergence of eczema;
 - Klaudia felt very irritable, but at the same time more focused;
 - in the following days, she had to take painkillers, but in smaller quantities and smaller doses.

Massage 2: Crisis and instability

- The second session made Klaudia think about continuing therapy. She felt good about the massage itself. She didn't feel the need for control.
- Negative symptoms intensified in the form of frequent headaches and increased cardiac arrhythmia. More migraines than usual were reported.
- She experienced muscle pain and swollen fingers, as well as increased eczema and higher temperature. In the following days, she felt hot and needed to have more frequent bowel movements.
- She experienced both positive and negative effects—on the one hand, she felt better, had more energy (she was in the mood for Pilates after work), experienced less stress, and felt more at peace. On the other hand, her body's reactions (migraines, arrhythmia) were cause for concern.

- Her husband was sceptical about the therapy (he prefers pharmacology) and was worried about her health.

Massage 3: Turning point and dramatic improvement

- After the third session, there was a breakthrough in the treatment, which brought significant relief from chronic symptoms. Immediately after the massage, the patient still experienced severe fatigue and muscle pain, as well as an increase in migraine attacks, but this was accompanied by a sense of calm in the mind.
- The migraines subsided. Klaudia stopped taking painkillers more or less 5 or 6 days after the massage.
- Pain during intercourse decreased significantly. Periods have become lighter and less painful; the pain is intense but shorter in duration (only on the first and last days, rather than lasting 6–7 days).
- Klaudia felt a huge sense of relief from stress and became much more composed. Her heart health improved. There was a noticeable physical change: she lost 4 kg, and her waistline reduced.
- Her sleep improved dramatically. Klaudia slept more deeply, fell asleep quickly, woke up less often, and felt more rested when she woke up.
- Her husband noticed that Klaudia was changing; she was smiling more often and looked better.

Massage 4: Releasing trauma and finding peace

- The fourth massage reinforced the positive changes, focusing on the emotional and mental aspects.
- Klaudia described it as a turning point marked by tears followed by laughter, which led to the release of her worst childhood trauma.

Course of therapy

- The frequency of migraines decreased, and those that did occur were no longer as severe (reduced medication dosage). Period pain decreased. Heart condition improved, which allowed to reduce the medication dosage.
- There was a dramatic increase in her subjective sense of happiness; Klaudia felt a deep sense of peace and began to appreciate herself and her life. Her body became much more relaxed, and the tension she had been feeling disappeared.
- **Klaudia finally got pregnant (after five years of trying and planning for IVF).**

Massage 5: Reinforcing the changes

- After completing a series of five Lomi lomi massages, Klaudia noticed a huge change in her life.
- The number of days with pain dropped dramatically. The worst episodes of pain occurred less frequently, were less severe, and subsided more quickly. She was able to manage the pain without taking any painkillers.
- Klaudia was able to cope with stress more quickly and effectively; she no longer let her mind run wild with worst-case scenarios.
- She stopped taking her medication for arrhythmia. She was able to alleviate her symptoms related to migraines, back pain, and bruxism.
- The lymphatic swelling decreased and her body looked better (as evidenced by her clothes and weight loss). Klaudia has grown to like herself and is happier.
- The therapy improved the patient's quality of life, motivating them to adopt a healthy diet, take up meditation and yoga/Pilates, and to change her job.

Results

Klaudia's therapy was a process of intense, though not always comfortable, change.

***At the end of August 2025, Klaudia gave birth to a healthy baby boy named Lucas.**

- **Deep detoxification and somatic response:** The initial massages triggered strong physical and emotional reactions (sweating, fluctuating body temperature, irritability, and even an increase in arrhythmias and migraines), indicating that the body was working intensely, releasing accumulated tension, and undergoing biochemical changes.
- **Lomi lomi as a tool for working with trauma:** The breakthrough came after the third and fourth sessions, when the release of childhood trauma was directly linked to the release of physical tension and pain.
- **Spectacular improvement in quality of life:** The therapy led to a significant reduction in chronic pain, stress levels, and endometriosis-related symptoms, making it possible to reduce or completely discontinue medication (pain relievers and antiarrhythmics).
- **Influence on fertility:** The most surprising outcome was that she became pregnant after years of unsuccessful attempts. Klaudia attributes this directly to letting go of her tensions and traumas during therapy.
- Klaudia is planning to continue getting massages during her pregnancy and after giving birth*.

CASE STUDIES

Joanna

CASE STUDIES – JOANNA

Age 56 years old	Duration of symptoms 47 years	Frequency of pain relief medication use Daily	Number of days with pain Constantly
Menstruation: „heavy, irregular, painful–I can’t function, I sometimes faint, I have to take time off work, and my period sometimes lasts two weeks” (perimenopause)			
Therapy objective: improved mood, reduced pain			

Joanna

- Joanna is 56 years old. She enrolled in the study because of chronic pain she had been experiencing for many years. At the start of treatment, her daily activities were significantly limited–she was disabled and used a cane to get around.
- Chronic pain:** She had been suffering from pain since she was nine years old, ever since she got her first period. She experienced constant pain throughout her body, which persisted all the time with varying intensity.
- Doctors' opinions:** “It’ll go away after the first child.” It didn’t even go away after the third.
- Multimorbidity:** She struggled with numerous health conditions, including endometriosis (multiple surgeries), fibromyalgia, gout, Hashimoto’s disease, hypothyroidism, heart valve regurgitation, and chronic migraines.
- Treatment and medication:** She regularly took strong medications, including opioids.
- Dealing with pain:** In addition to medication, she found relief in cold sprays, compresses, baths, and massages.

CASE STUDIES – JOANNA

Joanna's therapy evolved from intense physiological and pain-related reactions to an experience of profound relaxation and blissful calm, which led to pain reduction, emotional stability, and acceptance of her own body.

Massage 1: Physical activation and initial physiological reactions

- Shortly after the procedure, Joanna felt dizzy. She felt a strong need to rest.
- Her head and shoulders ached terribly. She felt “strange tingling” throughout her body (it felt like an electric shock to her).
- She went to the bathroom very often (to pee). She passed gas much earlier than before.
- Despite the pain, Joanna felt energised and was in high spirits.
- Breathing became easier.
- She felt safe and cared for by her therapist.

Massage 2: Relaxation and increased energy

- She described her second massage as “wonderfully relaxing.” The session left her feeling distinctly relaxed.
- She started experiencing abdominal pain similar to menstrual cramps, as well as a tingling sensation throughout her body.
- Joanna used the bathroom even more often. Frequent urination and diarrhoea became a regular part of her daily life for a while.
- In the days that followed, she had more energy, felt happier and more at ease. Her body felt well-rested.

- Joanna noticed that her body was becoming accustomed to nudity and responding to touch, which was important to her. She felt grateful that the therapy was giving her pain-free days, which restored her joy and zest for life.

Massage 3: Peace of mind and emotional stability

- The third session resulted in a significant reduction in emotional distress and improved quality of sleep.
- Joanna experienced a “sense of blissful peace” and “calmness of body and mind.”
- She began to experience sharp pains in her abdomen. Within 5-6 days of the massage, she came down with an infection—a cold.
- Joanna began to feel more emotionally stable; she was much calmer and got angry and irritated less often than usual.
- There was a significant improvement in the quality of her sleep. Joanna went to bed more regularly and earlier, fell asleep more quickly, slept more deeply, woke up less often, and felt more rested when she woke up.
- She described her session with the therapist as “a meeting with myself” and “a mental reset.” She felt complete trust in the therapist.

Massage 4: The metaphysical experience and distancing from pain

- Immediately after the massage, she experienced nerve pain and a tingling sensation in various parts of her body (from her abdomen to her back).
- Joanna went to the bathroom even more often.
- Her body calmed down, and her reactions to pain became much more detached.
- Joanna experienced the massage as a metaphysical experience and the therapist’s touch as a “touch of the soul.” She stated that Lomi lomi massage “heals trauma” and should be prescribed for endometriosis and depression.
- Her self-confidence and zest for life grew.

Massage 5: Embracing and accepting her own body

- After the fifth massage, her body felt more relaxed. Joanna was no longer afraid of being touched.
- Shortly after the massage, she felt a stabbing pain in my abdomen.
- Joanna went to the bathroom frequently. For a while, her body gave off a foul smell.
- The pain no longer affected her daily life.
- The regularity of the sessions allowed her to become comfortable with touch and with her own body. She noted that massaging the entire body is important because the patient is cared for “from the tips of their toes to the roots of their hair.”

Results

Lomi lomi has had a significant impact on Joanna's well-being and health.

Joanna appealed to the public and the medical community to show respect and trust toward patients, emphasising the importance of thorough diagnosis and not downplaying the symptoms of endometriosis. Joanna no longer uses a cane.

- Reduction of pain and of pharmacology:** Her "usual" pain levels improved dramatically. The number of "bad" pain days decreased significantly; the pain occurred less frequently, was less intense, and subsided more quickly. Joanna was functioning much better than before. She was taking significantly fewer painkillers. Additionally, the therapy also helped alleviate fibromyalgia-related symptoms, reducing pain episodes and relieving tension in the body.
- Improving quality of life and mood:** Compared to before therapy, her overall well-being and life satisfaction improved significantly. Her energy levels, which had previously been very low, increased dramatically. Joanna started eating healthier, exercising more, and gained self-confidence.
- Effects on emotions and the body:** Joanna began to feel more confident. She had a greater zest for life. Her self-esteem improved. She achieved emotional stability, became much calmer, and got angry less often. She began to accept her own body.
- According to Joanna, Lomi lomi massage is a therapy that should be available by prescription, not only for people with endometriosis, but also for those with depression. She emphasised that for someone living with chronic pain, participating in the program is a wonderful experience because it "restores joy and a desire to live."

CASE STUDIES

Agnieszka

CASE STUDIES – AGNIESZKA

Age 48 years	Duration of symptoms 20 years	Frequency of pain relief medication use Never	Number of days with pain 6-10 days
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Menstruation: regular, within the normal range, and prolonged cycles associated with menopause

Therapy objective: "I'd like to feel cared for and relaxed, because any nervous tension causes me pain."

Agnieszka

- Agnieszka is a 48-year-old accountant who struggled with painful periods and ovulation since she started menstruating. She has experienced severe symptoms for the past two decades.
- In 2019, after years of misdiagnoses and numerous consultations with doctors, she was diagnosed with stage IV endometriosis, with lesions on the uterosacral ligaments, rectum, uterus, and sigmoid colon, as well as multiple adhesions.
- Before beginning the treatment, the patient's health condition significantly affected all aspects of her life—it limited her professional, social, and personal activities, causing chronic fatigue and requiring her to constantly monitor her health.
- The patient managed her pain without medication, having completely stopped taking painkillers due to a loss of trust in conventional medicine.
- Instead, she used pelvic relaxation exercises, castor oil compresses, a hot water bottle, and breathing techniques. She rated her quality of life as low—just three to four points on a ten-point scale—because she lived in a constant state of tension and pain.

CASE STUDIES – AGNIESZKA

Lomi lomi massage therapy has brought Agnieszka significant pain relief, increased energy, improved sleep, and a profound and lasting positive impact on her emotional well-being and quality of life.

Massage 1: Awakening and deep detoxification

- An intense detoxification reaction in the body—elevated body temperature, bloating, gas, profuse sweating, cloudy urine with a strong odour, intense thirst, and more frequent urination, along with noticeable sinus clearing.
- Immediate improvement in breathing - a distinct sense of improved respiratory function, indicating that tension accumulated in the chest and diaphragm was released.
- A temporary pain in the area of the ovary—the onset of a characteristic stabbing pain in the area of the left ovary with a cyst, which quickly subsided.
- Deep emotion and psychological relief—a strong sense of physical and spiritual comfort, an experience of previously unknown gentleness and tenderness in touch that moved the patient to tears.
- A significant boost in vitality - a calmer mind, effective detachment from excessive external stimuli, a noticeable improvement in concentration at work, increased energy despite poor weather, and no need for caffeine.
- Food cravings as a bodily reaction - unusual flavor combinations (herring with chocolate).

Massage 2: Stabilisation and release of emotions

- Milder physiological reactions—cloudy urine with a strong odour, increased appetite, and a drop in body temperature—compared to the intense reaction following the first session.
- Short-term symptoms of reduced intensity—temporary, intermittent episodes of ovarian pain, a temporary sensation that menstruation is upcoming, but of much lower intensity than before treatment.
- Symptoms of infection as a cleansing reaction - the onset of mild symptoms resembling a cold (runny nose, sneezing, mild sore throat), but with a much milder course than a typical infection.

- The process of releasing past emotions—the emergence of intense, previously suppressed emotions, which required further work in simultaneous psychotherapy.
- Increased social openness—much greater willingness to interact with others, growing openness to interpersonal relationships, and moving away from isolation.
- Improved nighttime recovery—evening tiredness as a natural bodily response, better regenerative sleep, waking up on her own before the alarm goes off.

Massage 3: Changes

- An increased need for rest—a deep sleepiness that begins during the facial massage and lasts for several days after the treatment, as a reaction to intense internal processes.
- Reduced physical discomfort—only a brief, one-time sensation of a sharp pain in the ovary, and a significant reduction in typical symptoms associated with endometriosis.
- Increased emotional sensitivity—a greater tendency to cry, more frequent emotional outbursts, and heightened sensitivity as a manifestation of suppressed emotions and past traumas coming to the surface.
- Visible changes in posture and appearance—an upright posture, a genuine smile, and a noticeable relaxation of the facial muscles—changes noticed and commented on by the close ones.
- A significant reduction in premenstrual symptoms—noticeably decreased bloating before menstruation and milder symptoms during menstruation.

Massage 4: Breakthrough and a burst of energy

- The sensations were different from those experienced during previous sessions—instead of a state of deep meditative relaxation, the patient felt a surge of energy and a distinct sense of vitality.
- Reduction of pain—a very mild, almost imperceptible twinge in the ovary, which is the only symptom of discomfort.

Course of therapy

- A complete absence of typical premenstrual symptoms—no abdominal bloating, no mood swings, and no fatigue, which had previously been a regular feature of this phase of the cycle.
- A significant increase in social activity—a spontaneous desire to meet people, going out more often, and being open to socialising and making new friends.
- A key breakthrough in psychotherapy—beginning to truly and deeply work through the difficult issues discussed in therapy, consciously recognising her own needs, and allowing herself to accept help and support from others.
- A noticeable reduction in physical tension—a significant decrease in muscle tension of the entire body, greater flexibility and freedom of movement, and improved ability to cope with stressful situations.

Massage 5: Consolidation of changes

- Conscious, full engagement in the experience—the patient was more present in her body during the procedure, intentionally embracing every moment, fully aware that this was her final session of intensive therapy.
- Mild, typical physiological reactions—a slight twinge in one ovary of minimal intensity, increased thirst and more frequent urination, regular bowel movements—all of the sensations are very mild.
- Instant relaxation during a facial massage—immediate calm and deep relaxation the moment the therapist touched her face.
- Consolidation of results achieved—maintaining all the positive changes observed following previous sessions, no regression.
- A sense of closure—the realization that the intensive phase of therapy has come to an end, coupled with deep gratitude for the support received and the transformation achieved.

Results

Agnieszka experienced the multifaceted effects of Lomi lomi therapy.

Agnieszka found Lomi lomi to be a gentle, deep, and effective technique that influences both the body and the emotions.

- **A significant reduction in pain intensity**—days with severe symptoms occur less frequently; the pain is less intense and lasts for a shorter period of time, and the patient is able to manage it entirely without painkillers; even during more difficult moments, her ability to function is significantly better than before starting therapy.
- **A significant increase in vitality**—the patient has regained the strength to perform daily activities, no longer falls asleep while sitting, can read books without getting tired, participates in sports competitions in better shape than ever before, and enjoys better sleep and concentration.
- **Accepting her own body**—the patient perceives her body as being less tense; she feels more relaxed and at ease, and notices a visible relaxation in her face as well.
- **Complete elimination of lymphoedema**—the swelling in the ankles and feet subsided, and the waist circumference decreased by 10 centimetres (from 99 to 89 centimetres), indicating a significant improvement in lymphatic drainage and overall bodily function.
- **Restoring social ties and breaking out of isolation**—the patient reconnected with her friends, regained her desire to socialise and talk, felt like part of the community, and emerged from years of social isolation.
- **A profound emotional and therapeutic breakthrough** – the release of emotions allowed her to deeply process difficult issues in psychotherapy; the patient began to consciously recognise her needs and allow herself to accept help from others.
- **Making positive lifestyle changes**—paying closer attention to the body’s needs, adopting new health practices (cold water showers, Lyapko roller massage, moxibustion), and consciously limiting the consumption of sweets.

CASE STUDIES

Marzena

CASE STUDIES – MARZENA

Age 43 years	Duration of symptoms 30 years	Frequency of pain relief medication use Never	Number of days with pain It hurts all the time
Menstruation: „very painful, heavy, with large clots; I often feel nauseous”			
Therapy „I don’t expect anything. I’ve got used to living with pain. There are days when I think to myself that menopause is coming soon and maybe then the pain will go away”.			

Marzena

- Marzena, a 42-year-old teacher, had been struggling with endometriosis-related symptoms for nearly 30 years. Her health status prior to the study:
- Extremely severe menstrual pain:** The patient suffered from abdominal pain that often prevented her from working and carrying out her daily activities. The pain would wake her up at night. It was so severe that she ended up in the emergency room on numerous occasions.
- Years of ineffective drug therapy:** Despite taking numerous painkillers and hormonal medications, the patient did not experience lasting relief. Her long-term use of these medications led her to worry about taking excessive doses and to fear taking hormonal contraceptives, especially since she had previously observed a concerning progression of changes in her ovaries.
- Obstacles to professional and personal functioning:** Her symptoms affected her professional, personal, and family life. The patient avoided social gatherings during her monthly period and struggled with feelings of loneliness and a lack of understanding from those around her, including her closest family members.
- Emotional stress:** The patient suffered from recurrent depression and adult children of alcoholics (ACoA) syndrome, and her self-esteem was low. For years, she struggled emotionally due to a lack of acceptance and understanding of her condition. She rated her quality of life as low and her energy level as extremely low.

CASE STUDIES – MARZENA

In Marzena's case, Lomi lomi massage therapy led to a profound physical and mental transformation.

Massage 1: The first glimmer of hope

- Pain reduction: After the first massage, her abdominal pain decreased significantly. The patient noted that the pain did not wake her up during the night—for the first time in many years. She slept better than she had in a very long time, and the depth of her sleep was completely different from what it had been before.
- Physical remission of symptoms: Her abdomen became noticeably smaller, she felt a distinct emptiness in her abdomen (rather than a sensation of something weighing her down), and she was able to breathe more easily. Her tooth pain—a side effect of endometriosis she had been struggling with—decreased by 90%.
- An emotional breakthrough: During the massage, the patient began to cry. After the massage, she felt a great sense of relief and felt that she could see “a light at the end of the tunnel.” She felt heard, accepted, and understood.
- A shift in mindset and motivation to take action: After her first massage, the patient took a number of steps on her own to improve her health—she began drinking flaxseed oil, which has anti-inflammatory properties, adopted a healthier diet, and massaged her abdomen, all of which, as she put it, she did “out of self-love.”

Massage 2: Profound changes

- Waking up without abdominal pain: After the second session, the patient woke up without abdominal pain—an experience that was, in itself, a huge surprise and a source of great joy. She also noticed vaginal discharge with a consistency resembling cream pudding—a sign of the cleansing processes taking place in her body.

- Deep relaxation on many levels: The patient described the massage as an experience in which she felt as if she were “the cosmos,” and that the massage reached “even there, into some abyss, into some unknown regions of my being.” At times, she had the impression that she was being massaged by two people—she could feel four hands.
- Changes in lifestyle and mindset: The patient began to “be” rather than “act.” She slowed down and became more attuned to her feelings. She changed her diet (she stopped eating pickled foods and started drinking beet kvass), and she began reading books about endometriosis.
- Self-awareness and a sense of agency: After the second massage, the patient felt that she had control over what was happening to her body. She also realized that she was putting a lot of strain on her body and needed more rest.

Massage 3: The changes are intensifying

- Intense detoxification reaction: After the third massage, the patient experienced a detox day—she woke up with aches all over her body, as if she'd been “run over by a truck.” She spent the entire day in bed, too weak to do anything. She interpreted this as a sign of deep cleansing processes.
- Her period came earlier than usual, but she hardly felt any premenstrual cramps.
- A change in self-perception: The patient began to feel “more beautiful inside and out”; a “feminine side” emerged—a desire to wear dresses and jewellery, to be more “softer,” and to return to creative activities.

Massage 4: Change of perspective

- Despite the stress associated with her new job and life changes, the patient's pain subsided and became less bothersome. Her “pregnancy-like belly” also shrunk. The patient did not need to take any painkillers.

Course of therapy

- A positive attitude and energy to take action: After the fourth massage, the patient felt even more optimistic; she regained her zest for life and her desire to be active and creative. Marzena shifted her perspective from “something is wrong” to “I can help myself.”
- Significant reduction in symptoms: Menstrual periods became much less painful, and clots were much smaller than before. The pain no longer woke the patient up at night, which dramatically improved the quality of her sleep and recovery.
- Monitoring and conscious self-care: The patient began to monitor herself more intentionally, noticing when she was “pushing herself too hard,” and paying closer attention to her body's needs (getting more sleep, avoiding spicy foods). She nurtured relationships where she could “just be herself” and let go of connections that weren't serving her.

Massage 5: Completion of the transformation

- The last massage gave the patient a boost of energy and relieved her tension.
- The patient reported that her “pregnancy-like belly had disappeared.” Her waist measurement before the massage was 83 cm, and after the entire treatment, it was 76 cm.
- There was a further reduction in pain, as well as in the number and size of clots: There were times when the patient did not feel that she was having her period. The pain no longer woke her up at night.
- A shift in her approach to health and the ability to self-monitor: The patient implemented a number of lifestyle changes—she changed her diet, began taking regular walks, and started massaging her abdomen every day.
- Profound psychological and spiritual changes: The patient described feeling “more feminine,” wearing dresses and earrings, and sensing a “feminine essence.” She felt that she had come to accept herself, and began to view her efforts through the lens of “self-love”.

Results

The therapy led to measurable changes in patient's health and well-being.

“Therapy really helped me because I started paying close attention to myself. I learned a lot about myself. I was able to slow down. Be more present in the moment. Respond to my own needs. I was able to make different decisions.”

- **A significant reduction in physical pain:** The pain significantly subsided. The patient almost completely stopped taking pain medication.
- **Changes in the nature and cycle of menstruation:** Her menstrual cycle stabilised—every 28 days instead of every 22 days (previously, the patient felt as though she was menstruating all the time). The clots decreased dramatically, and the pain during her period became significantly less severe.
- **Physical reduction of symptoms:** The “pregnancy-like belly” disappeared (the circumference decreased by 7-10 cm), the patient was breathing more easily, her aching teeth and other painful symptoms of endometriosis subsided.
- **Improved sleep and energy levels:** The patient slept more soundly and no longer woke up because of pain. Her energy levels improved significantly. Although she still needs more rest than before.
- **Mental and emotional transformation:** The patient felt more accepted and understood. She discovered the power of self-observation, learned to let her emotions flow rather than suppress them, and today is rebuilding her relationship with her own body. Her depression has lessened, and her level of optimism has increased.
- **Change of life style and health awareness:** The patient has consciously changed her diet (incorporating anti-inflammatory foods and giving up junk food), gets regular massages, and pays closer attention to her body’s needs.

CASE STUDIES

Zuzanna

CASE STUDIES – ZUZANNA

Age 35 years	Duration of symptoms 15 years	Frequency of pain relief medication use Several times a week	Number of days with pain It hurts all the time
Menstruation: „They last up to two weeks; without painkillers, I can't function at all“.			
Therapy „Stress relief. If possible—both physically and mentally“.			

Zuzanna

- Zuzanna, a 35-year-old interior designer, signed up for a research program to see if Lomi lomi massage would help her cope with chronic pain and improve her well-being.
- The illness took a heavy toll on her personal, professional, and family life, having a particularly profound impact on her mental health.
- Due to prolonged severe illness and surgeries, she was forced to limit her physical activity, which made it difficult for her to accept her own body.
- Zuzanna had to undergo several extensive and unplanned surgeries (including two resections of the small intestine—one in 2012 due to adhesions and another in 2020 due to severe internal bleeding).
- She suffered from abdominal pains and headaches. Moreover, the abdominal pain was causing her great discomfort. Her surgical scars were causing severe tension pains, a “tugging” sensation, and a stinging pain in her abdomen.
- Zuzanna had irregular periods. Some lasted as long as three weeks. Sometimes she didn't have a period at all for several months.

CASE STUDIES – ZUZANNA

Zuzanna's therapy is a story of overcoming fears and building confidence, which led to deeper relaxation and a gradual improvement in her health and well-being.

Massage 1: A boost of energy and a sense of being in good hands

- After her first massage, Zuzanna felt euphoric and experienced an immediate burst of energy, which, however, faded over time.
- She had a mild headache and pain in the area of her left ovary.
- She noticed that she was breathing much more easily.
- She was going to the bathroom much more often than before.
- She was surprised by the quality of the massage, its effect on her body, and the therapist's remarkable calmness.

Massage 2: Tranquillity, initiation of changes in the body

- The reaction after the second massage was different from the first. Instead of euphoria and a sense of readiness to act, the massage had a calming effect. Compared to the first session, Zuzanna had much less energy.
- A day after the massage, she developed a strong headache.
- She noticed that her body was beginning to give off a strange, rather unpleasant odour, which lingered for the next few days. She continued to drink a lot. Her skin remained dry.

- Zuzanna felt that she was more composed and less impulsive.
- She began to think deeply about the pace of her life and her neglect of her body and mind. She became convinced that what she was about to do next was exactly what she needed.

Massage 3: Emotions and pain relief

- The third massage took place at a time when Zuzanna wasn't feeling her best. At that time, she was suffering from persistent, days-long pain in her lower abdomen, stomach, and head, which had begun shortly before the session itself.
- The massage really calmed her down, and the therapist adjusted her technique to maximize the therapeutic effect.
- After the massage, Zuzanna experienced severe pain throughout her entire abdomen, including the lower abdomen.
- The unpleasant body odour lingered long after the massage.
- She was more emotionally unstable than usual, and she was more irritable and tearful.
- The pain subsided after a few days. Zuzanna also noticed that her headaches were becoming less frequent and less severe.

Massage 4: Deep peace and a breakthrough in pain control

Course of therapy

- Her understanding of the process and her trust in the therapist allowed her to relax more deeply during the fourth session. Zuzanna came to believe in the stress-relieving and relaxing benefits of massage.
- She approached the massage with much greater ease, knowing what to expect.
- After the massage, she felt a slight stomach ache.
- The body odour was still different, but less intense than after previous sessions.
- She noticed that there were longer and longer intervals in her life when she felt no pain. The pain attacks still occurred, but they were much less intense and lasted shorter than usual.
- She started focusing more on getting a good night's sleep. She began working on giving up control.

Massage 5: Trust and deep relaxation

- For Zuzanna, the last massage was the culmination of a process of getting used to it, overcoming her inhibitions, and building trust. This allowed her to achieve a sense of deep relaxation.
- Zuzanna was experiencing abdominal pain and tension, mainly around her ovaries.
- She noticed increased urination and a different body odour.
- The need for control is no longer the most important thing in life.

CASE STUDIES – ZUZANNA

Results

Lomi lomi massage therapy has significantly improved Zuzanna’s ability to manage her pain.

After the therapy, Zuzanna felt much happier with her life than she had before.

- Pain:** Her “usual” pain level decreased significantly. The worst, most painful days occurred less frequently. Pain episodes were less severe, passed more quickly, and she even experienced days completely free of pain, which was a new experience for her. Even on days when she felt pain, her daily functioning was better than before therapy.
- Sleep and energy:** There has been a significant improvement in the quality of her sleep. Zuzanna reports that she sleeps more deeply, wakes up less often during the night, and feels more rested and energetic in the morning. She described her energy levels after the therapy as significantly higher.
- Emotional condition and stress:** Despite temporary emotional instability following the third massage, the therapy contributed to a mental shift, bringing her greater peace of mind. Zuzanna noted that she feels calmer and gets angry and irritated less often than usual.
- Impact on life:** Her introduction to the world of Lomi lomi led her to focus more on herself, her body, and her “inner well-being.” She began making changes to improve her health, which included trying to get better sleep and controlling everything less.

Discussion: an examination in light of what we already know

DISCUSSION

A study examining the effects of Lomi lomi massage on pain reduction and quality of life in women with endometriosis delivered promising results that should be thoroughly analysed in light of current scientific knowledge. These findings take on particular significance given the growing awareness that endometriosis is one of the most underestimated gynaecological conditions of our time.

Interpretation of results

- An analysis of the data collected during the study reveals the remarkable effectiveness of Lomi lomi therapy in alleviating the symptoms of endometriosis.
 - The most significant finding was **a significant reduction in chronic pain levels.**
 - The percentage of women reporting a complete absence of pain more than doubled. This significant improvement persisted over time, suggesting a long-term restoration of the body's physiological balance.
 - Changes in psychosocial functioning were equally significant. The participants' energy levels increased steadily, with nearly half of the women (49.3%) rating their energy levels at 8 or higher. Sleep quality improved dramatically, reaching an average of 7.81 after the third massage.
- These changes had a direct impact on their professional and personal lives—women reported a lower need for sick leave, improved concentration, and better interpersonal relationships.
 - Particularly noteworthy were individual cases, such as Klaudia's story, who after therapy not only reduced her pain from a 10/10 to a 1/10 and stopped taking her arrhythmia medication, but also became pregnant, as well as the case of Joanna, who for years struggled with constant 10/10 pain and opioid addiction, and after therapy achieved a stable pain level of 3/10 and drastically reduced her medication use.
 - These examples illustrate the holistic nature of the effects of Lomi lomi massage.

DISCUSSION

Potential mechanisms of effects

The mechanisms underlying the therapeutic effects of Lomi lomi massage are multifaceted and comprehensive.

- **Reduction of inflammation and support for the immune system.** Lomi lomi massage involves gentle, flowing movements that resemble ocean waves—and this is precisely how it can soothe areas of the body affected by chronic pain and inflammation associated with endometriosis. Study participants found that regular massages helped them feel less swelling and heaviness in their bodies. It's as if the immune system gets a boost to “clean up the mess” caused by the disease.
- **Release of tension in deep tissues.** Endometriosis forces the body into a constant state of tension—adhesions form, restricting movement and potentially causing sharp pain in the abdomen or pelvis. Lomi lomi works like “untangling knots” in the body—the massage therapist uses not only their hands but also their forearms, reaching deeper to release tense areas and restore the body's freedom of movement, which is often taken away by the disease.
- **Regulation of the nervous system.** During the massage, you can quickly feel the stress begin to melt away. Lomi lomi induces a state of deep relaxation in the body—it slows your breathing, calms your heartbeat, and reduces your stress level from as high as 8 to as low as 2 on a scale of 10! For many women with endometriosis, this kind of relaxation is something they haven't experienced in years—the massage helps calm the nervous system, which is often overstimulated and hyperactive due to the condition.
- **The release of endorphins.** During a Lomi lomi massage, endorphins—our body's own natural painkillers—are released. For some participants, the massage proved to be a truly transformative experience, bringing relief not only physically but also emotionally; many women spoke of a sense of “liberation” and “letting go of trauma,” and the massage brought them into a state of deep tranquillity.
- **Improved circulation and hormonal balance.** Every movement made by the massage therapist improves circulation, allowing blood to more easily deliver oxygen and essential nutrients wherever they're needed. Deep relaxation can even help balance hormones, which are often disrupted in cases of endometriosis. Some women noticed that their menstrual cycles became lighter and shorter after massages, and the pain less bothersome.

DISCUSSION

Comparison with other studies

The results are consistent with a growing body of literature pointing to the effectiveness of complementary therapies for endometriosis. A review by Mazur-Biały (2024) confirms that manual therapies can provide significant pain relief and improve quality of life. Comprehensive manual therapy led to a 30.76% reduction in pain and improvements in control, helplessness, and emotional well-being.

Wurn et al. documented that intensive manual therapy sessions led to improvements in the menstrual cycle and a reduction in dysmenorrhea (painful periods). Although the Lomi lomi protocol was less intensive (5 sessions at two-week intervals), the observed effects were comparable or better, suggesting the particular effectiveness of a holistic, repetitive approach.

Del Forno et al. (2022) demonstrated the effectiveness of Thiele massage in treating dyspareunia (pain experienced before, during, or after sexual intercourse) and pelvic pain. This study also reported improvements in sexual dysfunction, with Lomi lomi offering the additional benefit of a systemic effect on the entire body.

In the Polish context, the KOS-Endo system (Comprehensive Care System for Patients with Endometriosis), introduced in July 2025, focuses on surgical and pharmacological treatment. ESHRE (European Society of Human Reproduction and Embryology) guidelines emphasise that some women may benefit from complementary therapies in the form of improved quality of life. This study provides empirical evidence of the effectiveness of Lomi lomi massage as a complement to traditional treatment.

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Conclusions and recommendations

DISCUSSION

Practical implications

The findings have significant implications for clinical practice. Lomi lomi massage may be recommended as a safe adjuvant therapy, particularly for patients who are intolerant to hormonal therapy, awaiting surgery, have limited access to specialised care, or are seeking a holistic approach that takes psychological factors into account.

For the healthcare system, incorporating massage into treatment programs could provide economic benefits by reducing medication use, decreasing the number of sick days, and improving workplace productivity. International organisations, such as Endometriosis Australia, recognise massage as a complementary form of treatment.

Controversy. It is important to address the controversy. [Johannes Evers*](#) put forth the provocative claim that “endometriosis does not exist,” highlighting the problem of overdiagnosis. In this context, non-pharmacological approaches, such as Lomi lomi, may offer a valuable alternative, helping to avoid the potential risks of excessive medical intervention.

Critics point to the lack of standardisation in complementary therapies and the limited number of RCTs. This study was not randomised, which constitutes a limitation. However, the analysis of the observed effects, their magnitude (a 40% reduction in pain, a 30% increase in energy), and the multidimensional nature of the changes make it difficult to attribute them solely to the placebo effect.

Recommendations:

- the inclusion of Lomi lomi massage in treatment programs as an adjunct therapy;
- training physiotherapists in working with patients with endometriosis;
- refund of manual therapy under NFZ—the National Health Fund;
- conducting further RCTs with a longer follow-up period;
- the integration of a biopsychosocial approach into standards of care;
- public education aimed at raising awareness of endometriosis and reducing stigma.

Concluding, the study provides compelling evidence of the effectiveness of Lomi lomi massage in providing comprehensive support for the treatment of endometriosis. The observed benefits—pain relief, improved quality of life, reduced dependence on medication, and profound psychological transformation—make this therapy a valuable option for women struggling with chronic illness.

Given the growing recognition of integrative medicine, Lomi lomi massage deserves a place in the therapeutic arsenal of modern gynaecology.

* Reference: J.L. Evers, *Endometriosis does not exist; all women have endometriosis* [online] <https://academic.oup.com/humrep/article-abstract/9/12/2206/685433?redirectedFrom=fulltext&login=false> [access: 18 Nov 2025].

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

So what should we do?

Endometriosis is one of those conditions that can completely change your daily life—not only because of the pain and physical limitations it causes, but also because of the emotional toll it takes.

The results of a study—which drew on the experiences of women with endometriosis and the observations of Lomi lomi massage therapists—show that a comprehensive therapeutic approach—combining medical care with emotional and hands-on support—brings about a tangible improvement in quality of life.

On the following pages, you will find the main findings and practical recommendations from the study, organised by key target groups.

General conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions and recommendations for healthcare professionals

Conclusions and recommendations for women with symptoms of endometriosis

Conclusions and recommendations for therapists (massage therapists)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

General conclusions and recommendations

- * There is a need for widespread public education about the symptoms of endometriosis—it's important to make it clear that painful periods, chronic abdominal pain, and fatigue are not simply “part of being a woman,” but warning signs that require attention and diagnosis.
- * Efforts to raise awareness about endometriosis should target not only patients but also those around them. The more people who understand the condition, the easier it is to get support and proper care.
- * It is recommended to create and promote reliable informational materials and to share the stories of women who have faced diagnostic and therapeutic challenges—such stories have the power to change social attitudes and break down taboos.
- * It is important to reinforce the belief that illness is not caused by personal fault, neglect, or an unhealthy lifestyle—it is a condition that requires understanding and holistic care.
- * It is recommended to organise educational campaigns targeting various age and occupational groups—including men—to increase understanding of the issue and foster empathy toward women struggling with endometriosis.
- * We encourage you to see specialists regularly and to monitor your health on your own, as this helps detect symptoms early and allows for faster treatment.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions and recommendations for healthcare professionals

- * Any woman reporting chronic lower abdominal pain or unusual symptoms should be taken seriously and receive a comprehensive, holistic evaluation, without her symptoms being downplayed.
- * Healthcare professionals should continuously improve their communication skills with patients and seek out knowledge regarding modern and complementary methods that support treatment, such as therapeutic massage, relaxation techniques, and psychological therapies.
- * It is recommended that women be fully informed about treatment options—both pharmacological and alternative—so that they can make an informed choice about the best option for them.
- * Within the medical community, it is important to raise awareness that endometriosis is not limited to gynaecological symptoms—its effects touch nearly every aspect of a woman’s life, including her physical and mental well-being.
- * It is recommended to be more open to interdisciplinary collaboration—for example, between doctors, physical therapists, dieticians, psychologists, and massage therapists—as this approach offers the best chance for a lasting improvement in patients’ quality of life.
- * It is recommended to adopt an empathetic, non-judgmental attitude toward women with endometriosis and to reject stereotypes that may harm them or exacerbate their frustration.
- * Staff should also inform patients about the option of participating in support groups or receiving psychological therapy as part of comprehensive care.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions and recommendations for women with symptoms of endometriosis

- * It's important to listen to your body and not ignore chronic or unusual symptoms. Seeking help promptly can significantly improve the quality of your life.
- * Don't be afraid to seek a second opinion or switch doctors if you feel that your symptoms are being downplayed.
- * Support your health through small, daily actions—make sure to get enough rest, allow yourself to relax (e.g., massages, hot baths, breathing exercises, as mentioned by many study participants), and find your own effective ways to reduce stress and tension.
- * Involve your loved ones and communicate your needs—this will help you gain valuable support and the sense that you're not facing this illness alone.
- * Be kind to yourself: allow yourself to have some bad days, and don't feel guilty when you need a break. Your well-being and mental and physical health matter most.
- * Don't hesitate to try out different types of treatment (manual therapy, physical therapy, psychological counselling)—combining different approaches often yields the best results.
- * Sharing your experiences with other women can be valuable both for you and for others who are dealing with the illness.
- * Remember that self-acceptance and taking care of your body are important parts of the healing process—don't be afraid to enjoy massages, self-care, and exercise, which bring you relief and joy.
- * Keep in mind that the path to recovery from chronic pain is very personal—try to be patient and persistent in finding solutions that work for you.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions and recommendations for therapists (massage therapists)

- * Every woman with endometriosis requires an individualised approach—listen carefully, ask for details, and adapt your treatment approach to her current needs and well-being.
- * It is essential to build a relationship based on trust, a sense of security, and mutual respect. Ensure comfort, privacy, and professionalism at every stage of therapy.
- * Regular treatments and a holistic approach (working with the entire body, not just the areas of pain) have proven to be the most effective in improving women’s well-being.
- * It’s a good idea to educate your clients about the benefits of touch, self-massage, and relaxation techniques they can practice at home between sessions.
- * Be open to collaborating with other specialists (doctors, physical therapists, dieticians)—an interdisciplinary team delivers the best results and helps patients feel more secure.
- * Be mindful of emotional reactions during and after the procedure—they may be part of the healing process and a way to release tension. Show empathy and avoid judging mood swings; allow patients to experience their emotions in a safe environment.
- * Continuously educate yourself about endometriosis and approaches to managing chronic conditions—and share what you learn with other therapists and clients.
- * Make sure that the massage is always performed safely, gently, and with respect for the patient’s personal boundaries.
- * Try to inspire your clients to change their lifestyle and approach to their own health. Your attitude, kindness, and openness can serve as a motivation for positive changes even outside the office.

Unobvious statistics

List of Lomi massage therapists who participated in the study

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

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- Agnieszka Balcarek - Irlandia, Rathnew
- Agnieszka Kawula - Puck
- Anna Mayer - Gdynia
- Anna Paradowska - Kozięgłowy Poznań
- Anna Zdebska - Poznań
- Ásgeir Baldursson - Reykjavik, Islandia
- Celina Fit - Gdańsk
- Danuta Gosz - Gdynia
- Dobromir Czerkas - Łuków
- Dominika Światłoń - Kraków
- Dorota Leśniewska - Głusino koło Kartuz
- Emilia Tura - Jaworzno
- Grażyna Bieleń - Koszalin
- Grażyna Poseniak - Opole
- Iwona Kurowska - Kudowa Zdrój
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- Joanna Oppermann - Wałcz
- Julia Wiechowska - Nakło nad Notecią
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Lomi lomi Massage as a supportive therapy for patients with endometriosis

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